

Introducing Graphic Experiential Evidencing (GEE). How can the use of graphic novel fill a gap in the service design toolkit for communicating experience and emotion?

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Abstract With an increasing focus on experience-centric services, where deeper customer connection is to be achieved by heightened dramaturgy and emotional engagement, service design must ensure it has tools that can model and communicate these experiences during service development.

Existing methods of visualizing services such as the Service Blueprint, whilst good for modeling the structure of experience delivery, do not convey the richness of the experiences itself.

Graphic Experiential Evidencing (GEE) has been developed through a process of research by design during a design intervention for the improvement of stadium football experience, when existing service design visualization tools were found lacking for the communicating of the designed experience to stakeholders.

This paper describes work in progress that adapts the graphic novel as a way to aid in the conveying of desired 'on brand' experience and desired emotional response in context.

Interviews with those involved in the project as well as other service designers suggest that using GEE in combination with existing service design tools offers great promise. Results show that the technique gives the service designer new ways to deliver an experience sample and communicate projected experiences and emotion to clients during the development of new services.

Keywords *Service design, Visualization, Graphic novel, Experience, Evidencing*

Introduction

Suri (2004) quotes Moggeridge's well-known tautology 'The only way to experience an experience is by experiencing it'. She uses it as a way to underline the need for designers to use their visual skills and design tools not just as a way to convey insights and findings but in a fuller more experiential way for 'Developing common vision.....Creating richer representation.' (Suri, 2004, p. 16)

If Service Design is the design of experience (LiveWork, 2008) then we need to ensure that we have tools that can develop a common vision of the desired experience rather than just that of the system of delivery. Whilst companies are increasingly putting customer experience at the core of their service offerings (Haeckel, Carbone, & Berry, 2003; Pine & Gilmore, 1999; Voss, Roth, & Chase, 2008), the real

power of design is making the experience more tangible during the design process itself (Suri, 2004).

Service designers use visualization during all stages of the service design process. This paper focuses on the generative phase. This paper is authored by the service designer who developed the technique.

Paper structure

The paper opens with an overview of service design visualization, showing a gap in the disciplines 'toolkit' and briefly introduces the use of cartoons and the emotional response to the drawn image. It describes the context of GEE's introduction, insight into the technique and some examples. Then described is the method and the framework of analysis. The paper closes with a discussion and further work followed a conclusion.

Figure 1. (Halvorsrud et al., 2014).

Background

Service designers use visualization to make services more tangible (Kimbell, 2009; Segelström & Holmlid, 2011) and easier to communicate (Segelström, 2009), using such tools at the start of the process to visualize the existing service and to quickly sketch potential improvements and new artifacts.

The two main visualization tools for service modeling; Customer Journey Map and the Service Blueprint does not express detailed experiential outcome from interaction with the service (Won, Ko, Im, & Park, 2013), rather visualizing the structure of the service. The Service Experience Blueprint attempts to manage the experience across multi-interfaces (Patrício, Fisk, & e Cunha, 2008) but again is not intended to detail the experience itself. More recent work by Halvorsrud, Lee, Haugstveit & Følstad (2014) attempts to find a common language for communicating touchpoints within the customer journey modeling tradition.

Where this offers a standardized language of communication it does not address any deep contextual or emotional experience of the service moment.

Clatworthy, Fjuk, Kvale, & Matthews (2015) bring more expression to customers emotional response to touchpoints in the customer journey, beyond the happy-sad dichotomy to introduce precise mood words to describe the experience. What this work lacks however is the experiential detail of the service moment alluded to by Won et al (2013).

The use of storyboard is common across many fields of design (Curedale, 2013; Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011). Adapted from the film industry (Curedale, 2013; Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011; Segelström, 2010) the storyboard acts as a script and like the customer journey shows the flow of the action over time, however in a pictorial fashion. It puts focus on the interactions and touch points. The storyboard can express more detail than the customer journey, communicating the style of the service as well as bring focus to specific touchpoints and elements in context (Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011). The storyboard can be constructed in many media from simple sketches, to photomontage to other realistic visual representations (Meroni & Sangiorgi, 2011; Tassi, 2009). This may offer a glimpse of the experience, however it can be argued that the storyboard in many of its manifestations does not have the primary aim to

affect the viewer emotionally.

Evidencing as a service design technique can also offer some contextual detailing that can deliver to an extent a richer representation of a proposed service experience than the tools discussed so far. The technique warrants further attention from the academic community, though it is briefly alluded to by Kimbel (2009) and Suri (2004) if not mentioned directly. With much of the discussion taking place in the design blogosphere it is often used as Kimbell (2009) suggest as a way to describe the reaction to the introduction to a new service. However as Clatworthy (2008) shows when discussing his work with LiveWork, evidencing is used to give a sense of the experience of touchpoints in use. It does this by mocking up touchpoints and placing them in context. In this way it is able to include 'branding elements, design elements, interaction elements and behavioural elements' (Clatworthy, 2008). What evidencing in general doesn't expand on is the dramaturgy of the experience or a projected emotional response.

Though not visualization, other forms of service prototyping include service run-throughs and re-enactment. But as Blomkvist and Holmlid (2010) suggest that these forms techniques can lack authenticity. Furthermore due to the performative nature of service enactments, like the services they represent, they 'cannot be stored' (Zeithaml, Parasuraman, & Berry, 1985, p. 34) which makes them difficult to convey to those not present during the actual role-play.

Using cartoons

Clatworthy (2013) blogs that cartoons are currently being used as part of the visualization tool kit of service design to communicate service concepts as a way to communicate usage and to give guidance. He goes on to raise the point that the way product designers have drawn prototypes, especially concept cars, do it in such a way to caricature products to make them look more desirable. What the renderer does is 'simplify the reality of the object and turn up on the desire of the object itself' (Clatworthy, 2013).

The definitive description of the use, construction and power of the cartoon media can be found in McCloud's book 'Understanding comics' from 1993. McCloud highlights the difficulty of a definitive definition of the nature of the comic or graphic novel but lands for ease of use on 'Sequential Art' after Will Eisner. However

what McCloud points out, is that one of the skill of the graphic artist is to communicate with minimum elements and through the power of the drawings. This moves the technique beyond a reliance on a storyboard approach to communicate the narrative but to expressing the same through as few panels as possible. McCloud also argues that the graphic novel form achieves amplification of meaning through the simplification of the image. Here the medium allows us to focus our attention on the idea and through stripping down, deliver a form of intensity in a similar argument to Clatworthy. As part of the same argument McCloud then shows that this visual stripping down in expressing the experience of the protagonist in any story actually 'allows the reader to mask themselves in a character and safely enter a sensually stimulating world' (McCloud, 1993, p. 43). In this way the viewer can 'be' more than just 'see'.

This leads to the question of how a similar or relatedly appropriate technique might offer renderings of service moments that 'turn up' a sense of the experience and emotional, for the viewer to 'feel' the experience more. This is reinforced when we consider the neuroesthetics based argument of Freedberg and Gallese (2007), that suggests that the 'power of images' generate feelings of emotion and empathy that deliver 'a sense of inward imitation' (Freedberg & Gallese, 2007, p. 197) from the viewer, a mirroring of the emotion expressed in the image.

Context

Graphic Experiential Evidencing (GEE) was developed as a way to express experiences, in some cases the emotional response, the atmosphere of the service moment and when appropriate including touchpoints, as part of the project 'Alt for Norge'. A collaboration between the Oslo School of Architecture and Design and the Norwegian Football Association. As part of the

process it utilized many of the standard service design visualization tools mentioned above as ways to capture customer journeys and to convey insights from fans, stakeholders and designers. However when it came to the conveying the experience of meaningful service moments to decision makers, stakeholders and staff who were not directly involved in the project development, current visualization tools seemed lacking in representing the richness of the experience. To this end experiments using graphic novel were done to help in this communication where they were used in combination with these tools.

The technique

The technique became a negotiation between the vision of the service designer and that of the cartoonist. The style of the work was additionally informed by the organizations new brand values and esthetic.

This negotiation followed the following structure:

1. Understanding the service landscape and experiential goals
2. Sketching with the brand esthetics
3. Scripting by the service designer for the cartoonist
4. Preliminary sketching
5. Adjustment with further scripting
6. Final detailing and finished drawing

1. Understanding the service landscape and experiential goals

Time was taken at the start of the process between the service designer and the cartoonist to understand the goals of the project, the dramaturgy of the service journey and the experience that was being designed for. Comparative experiences were used to give a sense of the tone that was being looked for. These were things such as National day celebrations, being called

Table 1. Summary of Service Design visualisation and modelling tools.

Tool	What it is	Technique employed
Customer Journey	A modeling tool that visualizes time and the points of contact the customer has with the service provider at different touchpoints plotted chronologically along a line. Used for mapping existing services and for developing and communicating new ones.	Visualized as a two dimensional piece. Predominantly using symbols to denote touchpoints. Can include a customer emotion curve.
Service Blueprint	A modeling tool that visualizes the management of the service experience over time. It incorporates elements such as touchpoints but also front and back office staff roles. Used for orchestrating elements of new services.	Visualized as a two dimensional piece showing the layers of people, space and technology management
Emotion Cards	A pack of 12 double sided cards with positive emotional states on one side and the opposite emotion on the back. Used for understanding existing and projected customer emotions.	Printed on cards they are placed on the customer journey at specific touchpoints to express emotional responses.
Story Board	A modeling tool that shows the flow of the action over time in a pictorial fashion. It puts focus on the interactions and touchpoints in context	A two dimensional piece using photomontage and drawings
Evidencing	A tool that visualizes how the service might be or the response to the service if delivered.	Often a photograph incorporating elements or responses to the service, it might also be a mock up of a digital touchpoint
Service enactment	Not strictly visualization but an enactment of the proposed service to give a direct experience even if it is as such a sketch	Acting using makeshift props for touchpoints.

Figure 2. The call to Adventure. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

up to serve your country, emotive scenes in films.

The service journey was divided into a series of situated meaningful service moments. The cartoonist's task was to visualize these moments. There was some discussion about whether they would be individual panels or multiple panels for story telling also whether there should be speech bubbles or discourse boxes. However these issues were solved as the process went along, responding to the need of the visualization.

2. Sketching with the brand esthetics

Test visualizations were created to interpret the brand style into that of a graphic novel style. The brand values are Ferocity, Solidarity and Pride. Within the graphic novel genre the ferocity value was easiest to portray eventually settling on a style with a Frank Miller feel, which could be described as dark, robust and moody.

Pride and solidarity values could be expressed more easily through that which was being visualized.

3. Scripting by the service designer for the cartoonist

Service moments descriptions were sent to the cartoonist, including their purpose, the type of experience being designed for, touchpoints being shown. It was discovered that this was best achieved when written as a short piece of dramatized fiction.

4. Preliminary sketching

From here the cartoonist offered a sketch of the service moment. Here a negotiation took place between the service designer and the cartoonist about which elements functioned in regards to the service designer's vision, what needed to be conveyed and which elements should be adjusted.

5. Final detailing and finish

Agreed adjustments were then made and final cartoon delivered in digital form.

Figure 3. The call up. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

The images

In all 13 visualization panels were created. Some were loosely sequential while others were single panels. Some drawings included several panels that are not sequential, but attempted to show several elements of the same moment.

To follow are four examples of the artwork produced. These were shown to the informants, whose response forms the basis of evaluation later.

Figure 2. Call to adventure. This image intends to express the emotion and experience of the re-designed pre-match press conference. It shows the team manager in action where the focus is more on 'a call to adventure' rather than game facts and statistics. This is a non-sequential single panel.

Figure 3. Call up of players. This image focuses on the experience and emotion generated in a redesign of player call-up. Previously players were contacted through phone or email and the service designer envisaged a scenario where the experience for the player could be heightened by the inclusion of a 'call-up ritual'. This would include a befittingly solemn correspondence, a box and a shirt that would carry the message 'ja vi elsker' ('Yes we love' which is the first line of the Norwegian national anthem) hidden on the inside of the shirt. Here there is no chronological sequence, but 3 panels that show different aspects of the moment at once. It shows the touchpoints of the box and letter opened and players determined look as he understands his destiny.

Figure 4. The Arrival, is chronologically sequential. It shows fans arriving at the national stadium train station, approaching and then arriving at the corner of the stadium. These panels try to express the celebratory and inclusive feel of arriving to watch a national game. It attempts to convey the sense of spectacle and occasion

Figure 5. Music Together. This image visualizes 3 moments happening simultaneously at different

Figure 4. *The Arrival*. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

places. It tries to depict the sense of ‘solidarity’ when all are listening to the same uplifting music wherever they might be.

Method

Data for this paper was collected through semi-structured interviews from 9 informants:

- 2 informants had been involved with the broader project of football. As designers they were engaged in the branding exercise though not directly involved in the service design part of the project and therefore had no input in the process described here.
- 1 informant was directly involved in the project and represents the football association. Though not directly involved in the development of GEE, they did have input into the forming of some of the images
- 4 informants are practicing service designers.
- 1 informant comes from practice but currently works as a lecturer within the institution where the writer of this paper is associated.
- 1 informant currently works as a lecturer but also as a researcher within service design and practice. Both positioned within the institution where the writer of this paper is associated.

This mix of informants were chosen as they offered:

- An internal design view without being directly involved
- A stakeholder view that could offer insights into how the drawings were used
- An external view from service designers in practice
- An educators view
- A researchers view

Interviews were undertaken face-to-face with one performed via skype. All interviews were conducted by

the author. Most interviews were conducted with a single interviewee, however in one case two persons were interviewed at the same time. 5 interviews took place in English the others in Norwegian.

The interviews were conducted between 18th – 29th January 2016, with the majority taking place at the interviewees’ workplaces.

The interviews for the informants who had no prior knowledge of the process opened with a presentation of the GEE images represented in this paper. They were presented together with the customer journey, with some images of how the service was before and with some standard photographic mock-ups/evidencing. This was done to give context and this also represented how the images had been used during the project when communicating concepts to stakeholders.

Interviews began with an open question that asked the informants their thoughts on the technique through viewing the images, in the context of service design and its current toolkit.

Further questions related to the processes usefulness, usability and originality

When this information was not forthcoming further questions probed what they felt the images tried to express.

All interviews were recorded and transcribed.

These transcriptions were analyzed through a framework based on the theory presented above. This is represented by 2 statements, each with a pair of related research questions that put focus on the GEE model and its relationship to the theory

Figure 5. Music Together. Note: Both the cartoonist (holding 'ja' glass) and this papers author (holding 'elsker' glass) are visualized in the bottom panel. Illustration Syver Lauritzen.

Figure 6. Customer journey also presented to informants. Visualization: Ted Matthews.

1. The graphic novel form has the power to affect the viewer emotionally and to project the experience of the scene represented.
 - a. To what extent does GEE fulfill its intention of expressing and communicating more richly the experience and emotion to viewers?
 - b. To what extent did the images managed to project the brand values and could the projected experience be experienced through experiencing the images?
2. There is a gap in the service design toolkit for more expressive visual techniques for communicating the projected experience and emotion of designed service moments.
 - a. To what extent is GEE an innovation in process? (Given that the need of the project and the perceived lack of an appropriate tool in service design lead to its development)
 - b. How useful does GEE seem for service design practice?

Results

1.a To what extent does GEE fulfill its intention of expressing and communicating more richly the experience and emotion to viewers.

All informants' felt GEE was a good way to show both experience and emotion. This was expressed on general terms. However some went into detail, suggesting that the images managed to project an attitude, with others describing the images as powerful and with the potential to put across meaningful situations. It was uncovered that the images had been used by all the informants involved in the project for communicating the service experience to stakeholders to explain the experience being designed for. This was primarily for decision makers but the images were also used as experiential references for actors involved in delivering the service. For example the team manager was shown Figure 2, Call to adventure, to explain the perceived new experience tonality. These informants described an 'Aha!' moment when the images were viewed,

Figure 7. Stadium mock up also presented to informants. Visualization: Ted Matthews.

suggesting that they revealed something to the viewer. The cartoons however had been used in combination with other service design visualizations, such as customer journeys and mock-ups. They were also used with images from how the service currently is delivered and the contrast with these images they suggested have an additional effect. This was confirmed when informants from outside the project having been presented the drawings in this same way, felt they were more efficacious when used in combination with other contextualizing images and visualizations.

Where it was felt that the drawings communicated both experience and emotion, a couple of informants reported that some of the images themselves didn't hit the mark, either in terms of not conveying the desired feeling exactly of the scene portrayed or that the images had 'gone too far' and were over-the-top. In regards to the last point the informant suggested that this might be down to personal taste, however they did feel that image might be too aggressive pushing the brand values to the limit.

'Call to adventure', however seemed to 'work' for most of the informants and often was referred back to as most successful in conveying the experience. This could be down to the image having a single impact instead of having several panels that have to be 'read' to get the meaning; therefore the experience could be gleaned at once. But referencing back to McCloud it is in stripping down, that the cartoonist delivers the desired intensity and the 'Call to Adventure' is the most stripped down image in terms of number of panels and content.

1.b To what extent did the images managed to project the brand and could the projected experience be experienced through experiencing the images.

A number of informants expressed that they felt the experience from looking at the images (this specifically differing from feeling that the images communicated the desired emotion and experience well). Some of these perceived experiences were mixed with a sense of the brand values expressed through the aesthetics. The brand values were not revealed to the informants who were outside the project, however several suggested they felt the images were macho, edgy, tough and 'angry'. These descriptions match with the brand element 'Ferocity'. Others then suggested that images such as 'The Arrival', instilled feelings of 'patriotism' and in another case 'pride' and 'togetherness'. This matched with the brand elements "Solidarity" and 'pride'.

The informant working with football felt that the sport had a long association with comic strips making the media ideal for this context. In addition to this point another informant felt that the current popularity of comics made the images more readable for a larger audience.

Insight: This feedback shows that the graphic novel form operationalized for service design through GEE does convey experience and emotion whilst

communicating the brand. For some viewing the images did give them an experience of the experience. The single image appears to be the most successful in conveying these elements but to what extent this is due to its style and execution rather than its non-chronological nature isn't known.

2.a To what extent is GEE an innovation in process?

Using OECD's definition we understand innovation in process to mean:

'The implementation of a new or significantly improved production or delivery method. This includes significant changes in techniques, equipment and/or software.'

Most of the informants had seen the use of cartoons as part of the service design process. This has been mainly observed in the simple communication of the service flow and interaction sometimes in customer journeys, sometimes in storyboards. These cartoons were often little more than stick figures describing interactions. Cartoons are also used by service designers as a way to facilitate conversation with clients. These images then often remain in the process after this point as the customer gets to know them. None of the informants had seen cartoons used in this particular way or so 'expressive'. One informant felt that GEE represented an 'upgraded component' of the service design toolkit, where service design outsourced elements of the process to better skilled individuals. Others expressed that the technique had an advantage over media that convey the experience over time, like film or storyboarding, as it could communicate things happening simultaneously. It therefore allowed the viewer to take great leaps of context, that through a single panel it was possible to get the feel, meaning and experience of a key moment or meaningful situation. For a number of informants the image that used a single panel was the greatest departure from what they had seen before. Where a single composition through the expressive construction of the graphic artist was able to put across 'big ideas' and that through the cartoon form could take away elements that could distract the viewer from the 'meaning' of the designed moment.

2.b How useful does GEE seem for service design practice?

Beyond many of the respondents expressing loosely that they could imagine using the technique in their work others expanded on this theme. The informant who worked within the football association explained how the images took, the at times complex and near academic concepts and made them accessible for others. That they made less 'dangerous' and approachable. This informant went on to say they would need more as part of the on going work. Some expressed that getting the feeling and focus right using photos and mock ups would be very difficult and that such techniques can sometime feel fake and inauthentic. For these informants GEE as executed in this project gave focus to the elements that mattered, to the meaning, to the experience and emotion as you

are allowed yourself to fill in the blanks.

Several informants said that they would start using the technique in their own work and that others who had seen the work were looking to source cartoonists who could carry out similar assignments.

Some informants were concerned that the technique might represent increased costs that would be difficult to justify to clients. This view is tempered however by one informant who felt the technique could be used instead of and more effectively than expensive mock-ups.

Insight: As GEE does represent an innovation in process for service design it shows that there is a gap in the field for such a technique. The level of this innovation is not fully known and where it might not be revolutionary it appears to offer a fine tuning of existing techniques for generating experience samples. Adoption shows perceived usefulness. GEE also offers a real alternative to other tools such as the mockup for conveying experience and has an advantage over time base media, where the graphic novel can show simultaneous events in different contexts.

Discussion and further work

In general this data reveals a level of agreement between those who experienced GEE in use and those who were presented the outcomes, relating to the usefulness of the technique, its ability to communicate experience and emotion, its originality and as a useful tool in combination with others.

For a further insight it would be useful to collect data from those who received the presentation within the football association so getting a sense of how the images made the intended audience feel, rather than relying on designers who through their profession might have heightened susceptibility to 'feel' the projected experience.

Those outside the project were presented the drawings in the same way they were used in the project to replicate how they were used in practice. It would be interesting in further research to use two groups, one that viewed the drawings in context and the other that just viewed the images alone. This would help conclude if the drawings really do need the other tools to support their understanding.

Much of the feedback suggested that the single panel illustration worked best in conveying the 'feel', 'meaning', 'tone', 'emotion', 'big story' of the service moment. As has been mentioned this could be down to being able to understand the meaning and experience in a single panel. But as it was raised by one informant that their response to the actual execution of the image affected their evaluation, it could be the case with the single panel that this one just happened to be 'well drawn' for purpose. Here more research should be done where different styles and single or a series of panels could communicate the same service moment. With a test group this could give more insight into what works best.

Several of the designers picked up on the brand values experienced through the images. In addition it was suggested that the graphic novel style lends itself to football due to a tradition of cartoons and soccer in children's comics, i.e. Roy of the Rovers. Therefore further work is currently underway to try the technique in the service context of banking and whilst trying to reflect the brands values.

Cost was raised as an issue and the author can confirm that some images took up to eight hours to produce. However dependent on the client, type service and the potential of saving on producing other types of mock-ups the cost might be justifiable given that the technique shows advantage over other forms of experience communication.

Reflecting on the collaboration with the cartoonist, it was key to use enough time at the start to go through as much of the context as possible so they could really understand what the project was about. Also it became clear that trusting in the cartoonists own vision and skill lead to unexpected, yet superior solutions than the service designer could have envisaged. These aleatory responses in turn informed the further development of the final service design solution.

This study suggests originality and a level of innovation for GEE as a new tool within the context of Service Design. One informant used the word 'Upgrade' to describe the technique, but this was when comparing it to storyboarding. However the image that moved furthest away from sequential communication seemed to have the greatest impact and seen as the greatest innovation in conveying many elements of the service moment in a new way. The further tests mentioned above should uncover the level of 'significant change' that OECD alludes to.

Conclusion

Introducing tools of this nature has implication for the way that service design now develops over the next few years. This study shows that there are gaps in the current service design toolkit and there is much potential for the field to find more expressive ways to deliver an experience sample to others.

Graphic Experiential Evidencing does offer an expansion of the current visualization methods to detail the dramaturgy of the experience and desired emotional response for designed service moments. How radical an expansion is still not known.

In combination with existing service design visualization techniques, GEE communicates well the desired experience to audiences of stakeholders. Referencing to Suri, the technique does indeed create a common vision and richer representation, making the experience more tangible during the design process itself.

GEE also has great potential as a replacement or supplement to service scripts, where actors get to 'feel' their role rather than be told it.

More research needs to be undertaken to understand

further how the process might be developed and improved for repeatable, on target results across different kinds of services and in different brand styles. This research might show to what extent an experience might be experienced through this form of visual media.

It is hoped that this paper could encourage further research on how service design might expand its toolkit to encourage the design of increasingly experiential service offerings.

References

- Blomkvist, J., & Holmlid, S. (2010). *Service prototyping according to service design practitioners*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of ServDes.
- Clatworthy, S. (2008). Evidencing AT-ONE. Retrieved 29 September, 2015, from <http://www.service-innovation.org/evidencing-at-one/>
- Clatworthy, S. (2013). Comics as evidencing. Retrieved 29 September, 2015, from <http://www.service-innovation.org/comics-as-evidencing/>
- Clatworthy, S., Fjuk, A., Kvale, K., & Matthews, T. (2015). *Change by Design: Transforming organizational mindsets through Service Design thinking*. Paper presented at the Frontiers in Service 2015, San Jose.
- Curedale, R. (2013). *Service Design: 250 essential methods*: Design Community College Inc.,.
- Freedberg, D., & Gallese, V. (2007). Motion, emotion and empathy in esthetic experience. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 11(5), 197-203.
- Haeckel, S. H., Carbone, L. P., & Berry, L. L. (2003). How to Lead the Customer Experience. *Marketing Management*, 12(1), 18-23.
- Halvorsrud, R., Lee, E., Haugstveit, I. M., & Følstad, A. (2014). Components of a visual language for service design. *Proceedings of ServDes*, 291-300.
- Kimbell, L. (2009). *Insights from service design practice*. Paper presented at the 8th European Academy of Design Conference.
- LiveWork. (2008). Retrieved 10th October 2010, from http://servicedesign.org/glossary/service_design/
- McCloud, S. (1993). *Understanding comics: The invisible art*. Northampton, Mass: Kitchen Sink.
- Meroni, A., & Sangiorgi, D. (2011). *Design for services*: Gower Publishing, Ltd.
- Patrício, L., Fisk, R. P., & e Cunha, J. F. (2008). Designing multi-interface service experiences the service experience blueprint. *Journal of Service Research*, 10(4), 318-334.
- Pine, B. J., & Gilmore, J. H. (1999). *The experience economy: work is theatre & every business a stage*. Boston, Mass.: Harvard Business School Press.
- Segelström, F. (2009). *Communicating through visualizations: Service designers on visualizing user research*. Paper presented at the DeThinking Design, ReThinking Services—First Nordic Conference on Service Design and Service Innovation.
- Segelström, F. (2010). *Visualisations in Service Design*. Linköping University, Linköping Studies in Science and Technology.
- Segelström, F., & Holmlid, S. (2011). *Service design visualisations meet service theory: strengths, weaknesses and perspectives*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of Art & Science of Service, San Jose, California.
- Suri, J. F. (2004). *Design expression and human experience: evolving design practice*.
- Tassi, R. (2009). Story boards. Retrieved 26 January, 2016
- Voss, C., Roth, A. V., & Chase, R. B. (2008). Experience, service operations strategy, and services as destinations: foundations and exploratory investigation. *Production and Operations Management*, 17(3), 247-266.
- Won, J. H., Ko, S. Y., Im, E. J., & Park, N. C. (2013). A Study on the Service Experience Modeling Methods for Service Design. Retrieved 29 Sept, 2015, from <http://design-cu.jp/iasdr2013/papers/1707-1b.pdf>
- Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, A., & Berry, L. L. (1985). Problems and strategies in services marketing. *The Journal of Marketing*, 33-46.